

A TRACKING AND TELEMETRY SYSTEM FOR SEVERE MULTIPATH ACOUSTIC CHANNELS

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ABSTRACT

Underwater telemetry systems require special design when they are to be used in severe multipath acoustic channels.

This paper describes a modulation/signal processing method, called Spaced-Frequency-Shift Keying (SFSK), that effectively penetrates such channels.

SFSK includes features for reliable message validation, message identification, transfer of binary telemetry, and operation over Doppler ranges commensurate with maximum-speed underwater vehicles.

Although SFSK was developed for the specific purpose of underwater vehicle tracking, it is easily adaptable to a wide range of underwater communications applications.

VEHICLE TRACKING - BACKGROUND

Tracking, or locating underwater vehicles in real time, is a prime concern of the Naval Undersea Warfare Engineering Station at Keyport, Washington.

Vehicles to be tracked are outfitted with specialized acoustic transmitters and underwater tracking ranges are built by implanting receiving hydrophones on the sea floor.

Accurate measurement of travel time of acoustic messages, traveling from the underwater vehicle to the implanted hydrophones, is combined with an effective sound speed to give real-time slant range. Slant range to multiple-implanted hydrophones allows for geometric calculation of vehicle position.

Reliable and effective communications across the acoustic path is the main problem encountered.

Temperature variations, reflective surfaces, sea states, and noise (natural and man made) are all dynamic factors that defy precise, real-time characterization, complicating the communications task.

In general, the following are required:

1. Message Validation - Incoming messages must be reliably validated and arrival times measured accurately. Operation at the lowest Signal-to-Noise ratio (or Signal-to-Interference ratio) is required to obtain maximum slant ranges.

2. Message Identity - Validated messages must be identifiable. At any given time the acoustic channel may contain multiple signals that need to be identified as to source.

3. Telemetry - The ability to transmit free-form telemetry across the acoustic channel is highly desired.

4. Doppler - For underwater tracking applications, the system must operate at Dopplers produced by high-speed underwater vehicles.

SHALLOW WATER TRACKING - THE REQUIREMENT

The ability to track underwater vehicles in deep water has existed for some time and deep-water tracking ranges are abundant. Only recently have firm requirements evolved that require the ability to track objects in shallow water where slant ranges, compared to water depth, are very large.

Deep water ranges typically enjoy acoustic paths free from harmful reflective interference. Shallow water implementations usually do not enjoy interference-free acoustic paths and a new approach to the problem is required.

Additionally, in a shallow-water tracking range, the underwater vehicles are very near the plane of the implanted hydrophones. In this situation, Z-axis, or depth calculations become indeterminate and if depth is to be known in real time, it must be measured on board the vehicle and telemetered across the acoustic channel. For shallow-water tracking, reliable acoustic telemetry becomes an absolute requirement.

SHALLOW WATER ACOUSTICS - THE PROBLEM

In shallow water, direct acoustic path propagation seldom exists over any appreciable distance. Long distance transmission of information requires bounce-path propagation. In bounce-path propagation not one but multiple paths exist between the transmitter and receiver. Received signals consist of multiple replicas of the transmitted signal, all overlapping each other and continuing with decaying amplitude. Figure 1 illustrates the shallow water acoustic situation.

FIGURE 1 - BOUNCE PATH PROPAGATION

Constructive and destructive interference of the overlapping signals effectively destroys conventional modulation methods such as On-Off Keying (OOK), Frequency-Shift Keying (FSK), and Phase-Shift Keying (PSK).

Extensive analysis and field testing show that a new modulation/signal processing method is required.

SPACED-FREQUENCY-SHIFT KEYING - A SOLUTION

The modulation/signal processing scheme that was developed to penetrate the severe multipath acoustic channel is called Spaced-Frequency-Shift Keying (SFSK).

SFSK uses a time-expanded version of FSK as a modulation technique and correlation processing of a multibit identity code as a signal validating and identification technique. The time-expanded FSK allows information to cross the severe multipath acoustic channel without interfering with itself. Correlation processing supplies reliable message validation and identification, excellent noise immunity, and enhanced timing performance.

FIGURE 2 - ALLOCATED FREQUENCY BAND

To implement an SFSK system, an available frequency band is chosen and divided into four frequency sub-bands. At the receiver, a bandpass filter is needed for each of the frequency sub-bands. Filter bandwidths must be large enough to pass incoming pulsewidths over the expected range of Doppler shift. For the experimental SFSK system, the main frequency band used was centered around 35 kilohertz and each sub-band filter had enough bandwidth to pass plus-or-minus 2 percent Doppler signals (approximately 1400 Hz). Figure 2 shows the tracking frequency band.

Two frequencies, A and C, are used to transmit a multibit identity code in a time-expanded FSK mode. Previous experience has shown that a 20-bit pseudorandom identity code would supply the required noise immunity and processing gain for the tracking system. Frequency A is used to represent a "0" and frequency C is used to represent a "1" and the multibit identity code is transmitted in a long pulse string with each bit separated by a long quiet time. The transmitted pulse width in the experimental system was chosen twice as long as necessary to pass full amplitude signal through the front end sub-band filters, and the spacing between the bits was chosen to allow severe multipath pulses received to decay 6 to 10 dB before the next pulse. The experimental SFSK system used 1.5 ms pulses spaced at 25 ms intervals. See Figure 3.

FIGURE 3 - SFSK SIGNALS

A simple relative-energy detector circuit is used to receive the SFSK signal and reproduce a digital data train that represents the multibit identity code for that portion of the data train equivalent to the transmitted pulse train. The relative detector works well over a large dynamic range of input levels and needs only to make a continuous decision for each instant of time (whether A is greater "0" or C is greater "1"). Figure 4 diagrams the detector.

FIGURE 4 - RELATIVE DETECTOR

The output of the relative detector is fed into a comb correlator whose taps are spaced identically to the spacing of the transmitted signal and which examines the incoming data train for a match to the transmitted multibit identity code. The comb correlator can be constructed to search for and identify a number of multibit identity codes allowing for an expanded identification capability. The comb correlator threshold is set to a level which is a compromise between false alarm rate and signal distortion adaptability. The experimental processor threshold was set to allow up to two errors in the multibit identity code input.

FIGURE 5 - COMB CORRELATOR

Frequencies B and D are used to transmit telemetry over the acoustic channel in the same manner as the multibit identity code. An identical relative-energy detector is used as a receiver and the received telemetry data train is fed into a long shift register. Since the telemetry frequencies and the ID frequencies are separate and do not interfere with each other, the telemetry bits are interleaved with the ID bits.

When correlation occurs in the comb correlator, a timing mark is set which represents the time of arrival of the message. With this time known, the optimal time can be established for the pick off of the telemetry data from the telemetry shift register.

DOPPLER COMPENSATION - FINE POINTS

For applications where the signal source is close to stationary, the system described operates well. For vehicle tracking, significant Doppler can exist which shifts received frequencies and shrinks or expands the received message significantly.

Since the detector involved is a simple energy detector, frequency shifts can be easily accommodated by selecting appropriate bandwidths for the receiver front-end filters.

The problem of shrinkage or expansion of the received message is more significant. When Doppler shrinks or expands the received message, the individual bits of the message no longer line up with the taps of the correlation shift register.

Traditional methods of solving this problem are to phase or frequency lock onto the incoming signal and to use the locked signals to adjust the length of the comb correlator to match that of the input message. The nature of the SFSK message, however, is one of widely spaced bits of information and it was very difficult to lock on, or to lock on and hold, a suitable reference.

In the end, an alternate approach to Doppler compensation was used. The input detector circuitry was modified to create an input signal train that would validate in the comb correlator over the entire Doppler range. A fast-attack/slow-decay circuit (Figure 7), was added to each detector to, in effect, stretch each bit to fill in the spaces between the bits at the receiver.

The attack time for each detector was kept as before, commensurate with the rise time of the front-end filters, and the slow-decay time was chosen for an amplitude decay of 6 to 10 dB across the interval between the bits.

FIGURE 6 - FAST ATTACK - SLOW DECAY DETECTOR

It should be noted this tendency to hold a bit decision across the interval between the bits was already inherent in the received signal when severe multipath is present. The detector characteristics were, in essence, matched to the worst-case multipath characteristics of a simple energy detector (Figure 7).

As designed, the modified signal detectors detected severe multipath signals faithfully, but in situations where multipath was reduced or nonexistent, the detector provided the pulse stretching necessary to produce filled-in detected data.

With the expanded data train bits, the comb correlator tap points can line up with the input data bits over the full Doppler range of expanded and compressed messages.

FIGURE 7 - MODIFIED RECEIVED SIGNALS

Once validation has been assured over the full Doppler range, the timing characteristics of the comb correlator need to be considered.

Figure 8 is a diagram of processor validation time versus Doppler for three types of processors.

FIGURE 8 - PROCESSOR TIMING CHARACTERISTICS

Curve 1 indicates the timing characteristics of an ideal processor that validates at some constant delay with respect to the first bit of

the received message. This type of processor would be hard to realize.

Curve 2 represents the ideal timing curve of a truly Doppler-compensated comb correlator. If the comb correlator was adjusted in length to exactly match the length of the received message, validation would occur at the precise instant the last bit of the message was received.

Timing curves 1 and 2 are for ideal processors and give correct timing and slant-range calculations. Since a vehicle with Doppler is moving, the slant range is changing and each bit of the SFSK message originates from a different physical location or slant range. A processor with timing curve 1 measures the slant range to the vehicle for the moment the vehicle emits the first pulse of the SFSK message. Curve 2 is for a processor that measures slant range to the vehicle for the moment the vehicle emits the last pulse of the SFSK message.

Further, any straight line curve on the timing diagram represents an ideal Nth pulse processor. Curve 3 indicates the ideal curve of an Nth pulse processor which effectively measures the slant range to a vehicle for the moment it emitted the Nth pulse of its message.

In conclusion, actual processor timing accuracy over Doppler is measured as the best fit to any straight line where that straight line represents an ideal Nth bit processor.

PERFORMANCE - THE RESULTS

The performance of the experimental SFSK system is outlined below. Performance measurements were made for specific Signal-to-Noise ratios. For the following graphs, the noise power passed by the A sub-band filter was used for a reference band noise level. It should be noted that the total tracking band is approximately five times as wide and therefore if the overall system bandwidth is used as a reference the values for Signal-to-Noise ratio that follow would be reduced by 10 LOG 5 or approximately 7 dB.

The message validation performance of a single channel at zero Doppler is shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9 - ZERO DOPPLER VALIDATION

The performance of the system over Doppler is shown in Figure 10. Although the system performance does fall off slightly at low Signal-to-Noise ratios and high Doppler, above 10 dB validation approaches 100 percent over the full Doppler range.

FIGURE 10 - DOPPLER VALIDATION PERFORMANCE

Figure 11 shows the mean and standard deviation (one sigma) timing characteristics of the SFSK signal processor at 10 dB Signal-to-Noise ratio

Timing accuracy (one sigma) does degrade at maximum Doppler due to the character of the Doppler compensation technique, but at higher Signal-to-Noise ratios performance improves markedly.

FIGURE 11 - TIMING CHARACTERISTICS

As argued in the section on Doppler compensation, overall timing accuracy is measured as the best fit of the timing curve to a straight line representing an Nth bit correlator. Figure 12 represents the overall timing accuracy of the SFSK processor at 10 dB Signal-to-Noise ratio. Higher Signal-to-Noise ratios give improved timing accuracy over the full Doppler range.

FIGURE 12 - OVERALL TIMING ACCURACY

For tracking implementations, system accuracy can be enhanced by computer correction of processor timing. Real-time vehicle track can be used to estimate relative Dopplers for each message received, and Doppler timing corrections can be calculated from known processor curves.

The telemetry portion of the SFSK system does not enjoy the processing gain obtained by correlation processing and higher Signal-to-Noise ratios are required to obtain good telemetry data. Encoding of the telemetry data with an error-correcting code such as a GOLAY (23,12) will resolve this problem effectively, but at the expense of telemetry data rate.

Additionally, receptions of the telemetry message at multiple-implanted hydrophones allows for additional error checking and correcting.

CONCLUSION

Spaced-Frequency-Shift Keying represents an effective solution to the problem of penetrating severe multipath acoustic channels.

SFSK offers reliable signal validation and identification at signal-to-noise ratios above 7 dB (0 dB referenced to the total tracking band). SFSK also includes a telemetry capability, and operates over the full Doppler range of high-speed underwater vehicles.

Although developed for underwater tracking, the concepts developed here are adaptable to almost any frequency, bandwidth, and channel characteristics, and can apply to a large number of underwater communications applications.